

Review

Implementation of Inclusive Education for Learners with Intellectual Impairment in Primary Schools: A Case of Moshi District

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Abstract: The study explores the implementation of inclusive education for children with intellectual impairment by focusing on four specific objectives, namely, to examine the availability of teaching and learning materials for students with intellectual impairment, to identify classroom teaching strategies promoting children with intellectual impairment in academic performance and to investigate the availability of qualified teachers in implementing inclusive education for children with intellectual impairment in primary schools. This study employed a qualitative method in research where by a total of 30 respondents were asked different questions (7 parents, 15 learner and 8 teachers) participated in this study. The data were collected by using interview, observation and documentary reviews. Qualitative data were analysed by using the content analysis. The findings indicated the highly and inadequate teaching and learning materials for pupils with intellectual impairment, lecturing teaching approach, lack of qualified teacher and issues surrounded the environment of children with intellectual impairment low performance, less consideration, language assessment procedures lead to the failure of implementation of inclusive to pupils with intellectual impairment. This study calls for preparation of good environments to primary schools, employing adequate and qualified special needs teachers, using interactive strategies and teaching and learning materials to improve implementation of inclusive education to pupils with intellectual impairment in schools.

Keywords: Implementation, Inclusive Education, Intellectual impairment, primary school

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Introduction

In Tanzania, education is considered a fundamental human right. Inclusive education is a concept that enables students with special needs to be integrated and educated in regular classes by regular teachers. Recognizing barriers,

eliminating them, and providing suitable adjustments are all components of the inclusive education process that allows children and young individuals with disabilities to engage and thrive in mainstream education settings (Mnyanyi, 2009, 2014; Okyere, Aldersey, Lysaght & Sulaiman, 2019). Research has shown that with appropriate support, children who have intellectual and developmental disabilities can significantly enhance their academic achievements and adaptive behaviors within general education environments (Okyere, Aldersey, Lysaght & Sulaiman, 2019; Cole, Waldron & Majd, 2004; Fisher & Meyer, 2002; Avramidis, Bayliss & Burden, 2000). In Tanzania, as in other nations adopting inclusive education, children with disabilities should receive an education that integrates them with their peers, irrespective of their disabilities. This occurs because their separation in academic achievement prevents disabled children from having the opportunity to learn (Lewis & Doorlang, 1999; Bennet, Tunner, & White, 1998). As stated by Alamazi (2020) and Priyadarshini and Thangarajathi (2017), inclusive education can enhance the learning experience of students with intellectual disabilities. Furthermore, they mentioned that interacting with students who have no disabilities aids these students in grasping concepts more easily. Pupils with intellectual disabilities are provided the opportunity to focus on their goals since they are in a classroom with children who have no disabilities (Alamazi, 2020). In inclusive education, children with disabilities and those without can interact regularly, fostering their social skills and communication abilities.

The enactment of inclusive education encompasses several international declarations and national initiatives in Tanzania regarding the significance and delivery of education to individuals with disabilities. It is regarded as crucial as a human right within the 1948 Declaration of Human Rights, emphasizing an inclusive life and serving as a foundation for students to fulfill their potentials (Gray, 2013). Additionally, the Salamanca statement outlined the approach to achieving education for all (UNESCO, 1994). The school must cater to and assist all students. Education is global and acknowledged as a type of investment through which individuals cultivate an inclusive society and gain knowledge about their environment to fully realize their potential (URT, 2012). To establish inclusive education for children with intellectual disabilities, strong leadership is necessary in both regular schools and higher education institutions. In 1975, the United States provided free public education across all schools and stressed that children with disabilities should be taught in the least restrictive setting where their needs can be accommodated. The government supported the idea of putting the children in standard classes to promote integration (Berline & Blackhost, 1985).

A considerable body of literature (Alamazi, 2020; Bennet, Tunner, & White, 1998; Berline & Blackhost, 1985; Lewis & Doorlang, 1999) perceives disability as a social construct, which has held varied meanings across different historical epochs and cultural settings. This is evident in the move towards formal classifications and their connotations such as "Moron," "Imbecile," "idiot," "Insane," "Mentally deficient," "Subnormal," "Mentally handicapped," and "Learning difficulties." These categories reflect specific socio-economic and cultural advancements and the various ways in which policy and service offerings relate to distinct conceptions. Historically, individuals with disabilities have faced various reactions in both formal and societal discussions, including fear, hatred, pity, overprotectiveness, and condescension. Individuals with disabilities and their organizations are increasingly participating in offering alternative empowering perspectives, in contrast to those that have endorsed and legitimized disabling obstacles in both policy formulation and daily interactions.

In Northern Ireland, inclusive education has been a key educational concern for quite a number of years, with ongoing focus globally on government initiatives. Higher education institutions and schools that cater to the needs of children and youth with learning disabilities or other challenges. Those in mainstream schools should fully commit to the philosophy and practice of inclusion and should critically assess what they have accomplished to date. Nonetheless,

they acknowledged ongoing and diverse limitations both inside and outside their school. Inclusive education in South Africa aims for similar learning frameworks that facilitate essential curriculum adjustments.

In 2012, Tanzania updated the guidelines for implementing inclusive education. The Tanzanian Institute of Education (TIE) and UNESCO evaluated the inclusive education toolkit to assist Tanzanian teachers, school administrators, and educational officials in managing students both in classrooms and those absent from school. The group also reached a consensus on various Components to be incorporated into the curriculum for all educational levels and the national inclusive education strategy established to enhance educational practices by 2017. Prior to the launch of the national inclusive education strategy in Tanzania, several efforts were undertaken to guarantee the effective implementation of inclusive education. Haki Elimu (2008) along with Tungaraza and Lyakurwa (2006) discussed how perception, attitude, and insufficient pedagogical skills affect the execution of inclusive education. In spite of all these efforts, insufficient progress has been made, particularly in international declarations and various statements made by different organizations (UNESCO, HakiElimu, and Salamanca). Currently in Tanzania, the global community observes that a significant number of individuals with disabilities are unable to receive the education they seek from their nations. This resulted in difficulties in finding their future path, as they struggle to cope with the challenges encountered while trying to shape their future. This automatically leads them to poverty. The public institution is responsible for delivering inclusive education in Tanzania, including in primary, secondary schools, colleges, and universities. Thus, this research focused on the implementation of inclusive education for children with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Moshi District.

Statement of the problem

The Tanzanian government attaches a lot of importance to education and its role in the present and future development of the country. Through this, Tanzania has made an effort to promote the education of learners with special needs. Special education programs have been introduced to address the diversity of learners with special needs. Even with these efforts, the implementation of inclusive education for students with intellectual impairment has not been successful. There are still some problems to solve, such as the small number of these children in school, the lack of teaching and learning materials, the lack of qualified teachers, especially for pupils with intellectual impairment, and the lack of strategies for teaching them. Little is known about how children with intellectual impairment participate in teaching and learning process in inclusive education schools and classrooms that calls for research for developing understanding. So, this study looked at how primary schools in Moshi District included children with intellectual disabilities in their programs.

Research Questions

- a) What is the teaching and learning material for learner with intellectual impairment in primary schools?
- b) What is the availability of teaching and learning resources for primary with intellectual impairment?
- c) How are the curriculum implementation practices employed in inclusive schools enrolling children with intellectual impairment in primary schools?
- d) What are the classroom teaching strategies that promote children with intellectual impairment academic performance?

Literture Riview

2.1 Theoretical perspectives of the study

This research was guided by Systems Theory, which characterized the school as a social system that addresses all students to enhance learning. In 1956, Ludwig Von Bertalanffy introduced systems theory, which was further developed by Ross Ashby. The main principle of the concept is that a system comprises a set of interrelated and connected components that collaborate to attain a specific objective. The concept suggests that an organization is an open and organic system consisting of various subsystems. Consequently, a school, functioning as an open system, constitutes one element of students' (termed pupils in this research) human environments (Jensen, 1954). Consequently, anyone

who utilizes systems theory must adopt a holistic or integrated perspective to address various challenges within the organization or company instead of an atomistic strategy and method. In applying this theory, Germain (2015) asserts that teachers' views influence learning, necessitating strong mechanisms to alter behaviors. Consequently, the researcher utilized this theory to determine teachers' perceptions regarding the execution of an inclusive education program.

As stated by Bartaanffy (2006) and Meadows (2008), systems theory offers insight into specific elements as components of a system and their interrelations in certain contexts. A researcher successfully characterized more systems through systems theory, including management systems (educational institutions), communication systems (data transfer), and social systems (guardians). It is stated that the relationship between these elements influences CWDs' learning. This research suggested that schools, via their administrative frameworks, ought to take responsibility for encouraging parents of disabled children to enroll them in school for education instead of leaving them at home. Likewise, the research centers on the execution of inclusive education for kids with intellectual disabilities.

This is due to the fact that knowledge generated by educational institutions is essential in changing long-held beliefs within the community. Schools are tasked with enrolling students with disabilities and encouraging them to remain in school throughout their education by fostering an inclusive environment. In addition to the school, the School Quality Assurance (SQA) oversees, aids, and guarantees that the school, as a social establishment, caters to students with disabilities by offering education access in an inclusive environment. Consequently, the interaction of different systems enhances and supports the implementation of IEPs to provide the essential and fair education. The smooth transmission of information from upper management to lower levels ensures that elementary school conditions enhance, encouraging parents to enroll their children.

2.2 Teaching and Learning Materials for pupils with intellectual impairments

In the execution of inclusive education, teaching and learning resources serve as instruments to enhance learning and structure memory. Nyamubi (2003) states that the absence of teaching and learning materials leads to poor performance. The teacher's role is to choose and arrange the materials. In many cases, there is a lack of ample resources. It is highly challenging to sustain performance without instructional and educational resources. Mushi (2002) stated that insufficient teaching and learning resources contributes to the learners' poor performance. Teaching and learning resources foster language acquisition abilities including speaking, writing, listening, and reading. Teaching aids ought to be utilized during a learning activity to stimulate students' curiosity.

Hinzen (2000) observes that students and instructors commonly interact with educational resources as a way for them to gain knowledge and skills. As stated by Coombs (1995), teaching resources are utilized to enhance learning, sustain engagement, introduce diversity to the lesson, and connect one subject to others. Access to educational resources usually fosters learning in any program. Consequently, these resources should be sufficient for children to use them effectively. The presence of educational resources significantly impacts academic results. Educational resources are fundamental necessities for learning and should be accessible to students in sufficient quantity and quality when needed for effective curriculum execution. Moreover, it is essential to acknowledge different teaching methods to ensure that students with intellectual disabilities can gain from them alongside their peers' education (Armstrong, Armstrong and Barton, 2016). Inclusive education is advantageous for both teachers and students, as it allows everyone to participate (Kirillova & Faizrakhmanova, 2016).

Walkin (2000) noted that teaching aids help to expand the channels for information communication and provide a range of sensory experiences. Before educators can utilize teaching aids, it is essential for them to become acquainted with their use and application. He also mentioned that it is very challenging to sustain attention for durations exceeding approximately fifteen minutes without engaging the students in active participation. Utilizing different educational resources can assist teachers in recognizing the unique developmental variances, particularly in students with intellectual growth issues. If educators are inclined to utilize the same textbooks for every student, apply identical

techniques for all students in the classroom, and anticipate that they will react uniformly to the material they have studied. Nevertheless, utilizing teaching aids in the classroom necessitates careful preparation by the instructor. Maundu (1993) indicates that discrepancies in the quality and quantity of teaching/learning and resources imply that students receive a quality education.

Thungu, Gachie, and Alumanda (2008) highlighted the significance of teaching and learning resources for several reasons: they improve retention, leading to more lasting learning, they spark and maintain student interest, they offer direct experience with the physical and social world, they foster active involvement from learners, they simplify concept explanation for teachers, and they allow explanations to be concise and efficient. Additionally, they assist learners in enhancing their imagination, observation, reasoning, and creativity skills, while also fostering abilities like cooperation and sharing. Educational facilities usually draw students' interest, and once they have learned, the knowledge can be stored in memory for an extended period. The issue persists, as the absence of educational resources encourages a teacher-centric approach. Children grasp concepts better through hands-on experiences or visual tools rather than through abstract methods.

The research conducted by Krohn-Nydal (2008) suggests that essential resources like books and necessary educational tools for children with disabilities were lacking. Nonetheless, the analysis reveals that in certain classrooms, the teacher utilized improvised teaching tools. Insufficient resources like teaching materials and books, along with an unfavorable teacher/pupil ratio, were cited by all schools as barriers to the advancement of inclusive education in Tanzania's primary schools.

2.3 Enrolment of students with special need in primary schools

Enrolling students with special needs in primary schools poses difficulties in numerous developing nations. Illegan (2000) in the Philippines utilized enrollment records from the Department of Education for 1997-1998, demonstrating that among 3.5 million disabled children of school age, only 40,710 are attending schools, which corresponds to 1.6 percent. In the Asia-Pacific Region, the total enrollment rate for children with disabilities is thought to be under 5 percent. The research conducted by Lehtomark et al. (2000) regarding "case strengthening social networks within and around schools in the Maputo province of Mozambique" revealed that, from a total of 170,000 children in regular schools, only 1,167 were children with special needs, accounting for 0.7%. The enrollment rate for students with intellectual disabilities in special needs education is significantly lower than that of students without any difficulties. Mengesha's (2000) research in Ethiopia focused on education for individuals with special needs.

In spite of all the attempts by MoEVT to ensure education is accessible, certain groups of individuals and communities have not experienced equitable access, with some denied this right due to their physical and mental disabilities. ETP, (1998). Survey on Disability in Tanzania carried out by the National Bureau of Statistics. NBS, (2008) demonstrated the distribution of the 362,847 children with disabilities aged 4 to 14 years according to age and gender. Among primary school children aged 7-14 years, just 38.4 percent were enrolled in school. The number of children with disabilities fell short of the MDGs target, which aimed for a 100 percent primary enrollment by 2015.

2.4 The classroom teaching strategies for children with intellectual impairment

Jacob, Game, and Vakalisa (2002) assert that "teaching and methods pertain to how the educator conveys knowledge to students." An educator for special needs students must use different approaches when providing instruction to cater to the diverse needs of the learners. Ngoda (2007) asserts that "employing different strategies engages students, increasing the likelihood that they will learn, remember, and process the information given." The process of teaching and learning features two engaged participants in the classroom: the teacher and the students, and the responsibility for language learning in special needs pupils is not solely on the teacher. The students must take on greater responsibility for the learning journey (Quist, 2000). Vuzo (2010) stated, "Teachers and pupils engage in interaction, collaborating to develop intellectual and practical activities that influence the structure and substance of the subject matter." Nonetheless, this scenario is rarely observed in primary schools during the teaching and learning process, resulting in passive learning.

A successful teaching approach is one of the most important elements for achieving quality education. Successful teaching methods foster a positive classroom environment that promotes learning, conveys knowledge, and applies effectively. Unsatisfactory outcomes for students with special needs can be attributed to the teachers' inability to convey the essential knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to the students. Everything a teacher does or neglects to do in the classroom impacts the students (Mateo, 2011). The inclusive education curriculum includes a broad context, methodology, and evaluation process, acknowledging and appreciating the diverse nature of the school population in the teaching and learning process (Carballo, Morgado & Cortés-Vega, 2021). An inclusive curriculum recognizes the life experiences of every student, irrespective of their gender, origin, religion, ethnicity, race, cultural and linguistic background, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, age, and ability or disability (Swart & Pettipher, 2007). It ought to be fostering a learning space that acknowledges and affirms the variety and complexity of individual experiences. It must highlight the strengths while also addressing the needs of every child in the classroom.

As per Kochung (2003), the curriculum in Tanzania is strongly centralized, featuring frameworks that define the desirable learning outcomes for students, which are further evaluated through examination methods. The curriculum is structured with little flexibility and is typically content-rich. This type of curriculum does not align well with an inclusive education system. A strict curriculum often excludes students with special educational needs and pushes them out of regular education. It is not simple to restrict the range of inclusive education to be part of the curriculum. Consequently, creating educational materials that address students' needs and cultural contexts is challenging. Johnson (1994) emphasizes the necessity for a flexible curriculum that is process-oriented.

2.5 Teacher for inclusive education for children with intellectual impairment

The educator is the main resource for attaining the objective of an inclusive education and training framework (Paseka & Schwab, 2020; Swart and Pettipher, 2007). Consequently, it is essential for education that teachers receive proper training to meet new educational demands. Landsberg (2005) states that for effective inclusive teaching, educators require thorough and systematic training, either integrated into their initial preparation or through well-designed in-service training conducted by skilled and knowledgeable individuals. As the center of classroom teaching and curriculum implementation, a teacher plays a crucial role in the quality of education provided. Swart and Pettipher (2007) view educators as a crucial influence on the quality of inclusive education. Teacher competencies are a key aspect of both teaching and learning. They grew more discerning when considering inclusion. Thus, if they provide assistance to handle an inclusive classroom. Educators play a crucial role in the effective execution of an inclusive education policy, and their skills in this area are essential.

Hay, Smit, and Paulsen (2001) stress that the successful execution of the program relies on the high caliber of professional training for teachers at all levels to enhance and refresh their knowledge in teaching inclusive education. In this context, Winter (2006) mentioned that teachers eager to enhance their skills must be trained in various areas to ensure their contributions are valuable. Additionally, educators ought to be proficient in communication abilities and collaborative efforts across various fields. This assists the teacher in recognizing various typical disabilities, behavior management, the impact of poverty, and social deprivation via evaluation methods. If teachers lack knowledge and skills in inclusive education, their effectiveness decreases; however, when they acquire such knowledge and skills, their efficiency increases.

Heward (2006) contends that certain teachers are concerned about having students with special education needs in their classrooms if they have not received adequate training and support. Educating teachers on inclusion promotes adaptable teaching that employs diverse methods to accommodate various learning styles. Peter (2003) aims to assist marginalized students facing educational barriers by considering the local context, including input from parents and District Special Needs Education Officers, to ensure continuous services for pupils with special needs.

2.6 Empirical studies

Okyere et al. (2019) performed a scoping study aimed at improving comprehension of approaches that support the integration of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities into inclusive educational environments in Africa. The results of the study were obtained through an in-depth analysis of current academic literature related to the topic. An extensive search approach was utilized, which included querying five academic databases and conducting an additional manual search of notable journals and pertinent references cited in the selected articles. Two authors conducted the paper screening objectively using a reference manager named Covidence, which aided in maintaining blinding throughout the process. In cases of contention, a third author was approached for guidance. The research included a total of thirty articles that provided empirical evidence related to the execution of inclusive education. Eight academic papers highlighted and stressed various practices that support the integration and inclusion of children with intellectual and developmental difficulties. The application of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model clarified that the execution of inclusive education is influenced by multiple factors functioning at the bio level, micro level, meso level, and macro level. The findings also indicated that the idea of inclusion goes beyond just teacher participation, requiring substantial commitment from other important stakeholders, such as families and government agencies. To guarantee the effective inclusion of children with special education needs, especially those with intellectual and developmental disabilities, it is recommended to adopt a set of practices that have been confirmed through thorough research. These practices ought to be helpful and unique, while also being relevant across different areas in Africa.

A total of 49 participants took part. Content analysis was used to analyze the data. Results showed varying opinions regarding participation in standard classes versus specialized classes. Teachers who received training in special education possessed skills that enhanced their ability to facilitate learning, unlike their peers. The research determined that educators' training in special needs education was regarded as a crucial element for achieving successful inclusive education. Additionally, the study recommended that all educators in inclusive education environments, including those instructing classes with children who have intellectual disabilities, undergo training to assist children with intellectual impairment. Mnyanyi (2023) examined intervention services for individuals with disabilities in Tanzania since 1961. Data was gathered through Google Scholar and an empirical study involving 26 participants (13 teachers trained in special needs, 9 individuals with disabilities, and 4 parents of children with disabilities) who were chosen to take part in this research. The selection of these respondents (13 experts and 13 recipients of intervention services) was done using purposive and snowball sampling methods. Results showed fewer intervention services for individuals with intellectual disabilities due to the absence of a tailored curriculum, resulting in a lack of benefit from the general curriculum.

2.6 Knowledge Gap

In this chapter, passed through different literatures and what they say about involving intellectual impairment pupils in inclusive education. However, several concepts related to this topic have been discussed especially those based on implementation of inclusive in primary school. The intention of doing this research was to assess the implementation of inclusive education for children with intellectual impairment in Moshi District Primary school.

Research Methodology

In this study, a qualitative approach was used to obtain information with regard to implementation of inclusive education to children with intellectual disability. The idea was to gauge implementation status and gain reasons for the status of implementation that needed data and explanations from the stakeholders participating in the study (Engelbrecht & Savolainen, 2018; Omary, 2011; Stevens & Wurf, 2020). The qualitative approach was used to give deep description on the implementation of inclusive education for children with intellectual impairment in Moshi District primary schools. In this research, it was important to utilize a case design study since multiple cases were examined across four primary schools in Moshi District. In the study, a total of 30 participants took part in the interviews. Four schools participated in the study, the school sewer selected basing on numbers of impaired students in a particular school. Document analysis and observation were also used as part of data collection in the study. Purposive sampling

was used to select teachers, impaired learners, parents and school leaders. The data collected were analysed using themes and presented in the discussion and findings. Ethical consideration was also put in place as participants were oriented on the study and reasons for conducted the study.

4 Findings and discussions

4.1 Teaching and learning resources for pupils with intellectual impairment

To facilitate teaching and learning process, there are materials that need to be provide and avail in the classroom.

4.1.1 Availability of teaching and learning materials for inclusion of children with intellectual impairments

The initial goal investigated the accessibility of educational resources for students with intellectual disabilities in secondary schools. The study investigated teaching and learning materials for children with intellectual impairments to assess how these resources contribute to enhancing the academic performance of these children. To achieve this goal, the researcher aimed to address the question of assessing the accessibility of teaching and learning resources for children with intellectual disabilities in fostering inclusive education. The research gathered data from four primary schools that practice inclusive education concerning the accessibility of teaching and learning resources for students with intellectual disabilities. This was due to negative attitudes from both parents and teachers, along with an environment that is not supportive for primary students with intellectual disabilities. This is due to the fact that the infrastructures are not accommodating for children with intellectual disabilities. Classrooms lack ramps, and the offered classes do not provide adequate support. There are no restrooms, study areas, or play spaces for children with disabilities. Thus, accommodating children with intellectual disabilities in regions lacking improved infrastructure is quite challenging. Infrastructures have been constructed solely for non-disabled children, even though we are working to make improvements. Primary schools do not implement inclusive education specifically for students with intellectual disabilities, as there is a lack of teaching and learning resources for secondary students with special needs. The selected primary schools did not provide an appropriate environment for students with disabilities to study effectively like their peers. The information gathered through observation indicates that a shortage of books in schools could adversely affect students' academic performance and hinder the curriculum's implementation. The observations indicated a lack of books specified in the syllabus, suggesting that students received only partial instruction, which could have led to poor performance.

4.1.2 Availability of teachers for inclusion of children with intellectual impairments

The research investigated the presence of qualified teachers in the execution of inclusive education for children with intellectual disabilities in primary schools. To achieve this aim, the researcher aimed to address the question of what perspectives teachers hold regarding the implementation of inclusive education for children with intellectual disabilities in primary schools. The researcher aimed to understand the role of trained teachers in schools that practice inclusive education. The researcher observed that schools had certain chances to assist teachers.

We requested teachers who possess the knowledge and skills to facilitate the learning of children with intellectual impairment in various schools to assist others in acquiring basic skills and knowledge to support these children, but some have not participated in this. We simply wait for the government to hire those teachers. Our school lacks the resources to offer training because of budget constraints (Teacher 5, 2024).

One of the respondents (Teacher 5) expressed a necessity for educators for students with intellectual disabilities in schools. As per the information from the District Education Office (2020), the teacher-to-student ratio in primary schools in Moshi District for students with intellectual disabilities is 1:17, meaning one qualified teacher for every seventeen students with intellectual impairment. This indicates that there is a lack of teachers, as the necessary ratio for teaching inclusive education is one teacher for every six students with intellectual disabilities.

4.2 Curriculum implementation practices for children with intellectual impairment in schools

The curriculum implementation in terms of teaching process, assessment, placement, and care of learners with intellectual impairment in schools enrolling children with intellectual implementation was one of the objectives in this

study. The idea behind was that if the curriculum is not well implemented, children with intellectual impairment might face challenges in their learning process. This section is divided into two parts: enrolment and part two is about teaching process, assessment, placement, and care.

4.1.1 The Enrolment of Children With Intellectual Impairment

This study investigated the enrollment of children with intellectual impairments in Primary schools to assess the implementation of inclusive education for these children. To achieve this goal, the researcher aimed to address the question regarding how the curriculum is implemented in inclusive schools that accommodate children with intellectual disabilities in primary schools within Moshi District. Educators believed that numerous children experience obstacles to school enrollment stemming from various factors such as learning ability, social background, and the capability of teachers to support their learning.

Many children with intellectual disabilities are born like this; they are unable to function like an average person. Their capacity to learn or lead an independent life is restricted, so some require assistance in various areas for the entirety of their lives. This results in a limited acceptance of them in schools (Teacher2, 2024).

4.1.2 Teaching Process, Assessment, Placement, and Care

Educators, guardians, and students were requested to share their opinions on the teaching process, evaluation, placement, and support. Educators believed that teaching was difficult since they lacked an instructional guide to aid in facilitating student learning. One of the educators praised.....

During our time at the college, we had course modules designed specifically to aid in the learning of children with intellectual disabilities. However, both during my teaching practice and now as an educator, I have not encountered a curriculum aimed at supporting the learning of these children. Consequently, every teacher instructs these students in ways they choose, leading to some remaining in school for more than 10 years while others leave because they struggle with the mainstream curriculum. In a similar vein regarding assessment, as an expert in special education, I conduct functional assessments that are typically at the core of general curriculum assessments that students are unable to follow (Teacher 3, 2024).

The teacher 3 highlights key concerns regarding curriculum implementation, emphasizing the enhancement of learning practices and the streamlining of assessment. Typically, evaluations for children with intellectual disabilities emphasize functional assessment and seldom cognitive assessment that necessitates adjusted curriculum (Adeniyi & Omigbodun, 2016; Wong, 2015).

Parents believed that their children should receive education in a separate class for special attention. Parents expressed with concern that their children, beyond attending school, required additional support due to their treatment at home and feared they might face bullying if placed in a standard class. I was reluctant to enroll my child in school as I feared they would be treated poorly by other children without disabilities. You know my child has an intellectual disability, so in addition to attending school, they require special treatment. Will eat at a slower rate, cannot perform tasks and cannot speak as well as others, making them likely to face bullying (Parent 5, 2024).

Conversely, educators trained in special education and general teachers held varied perspectives. The educators specialized in special education believed that these children are unable to adhere to the standard curriculum and should be educated in separate classes with activities tailored to their specific disabilities. They also sensed being in a distinct group, as teachers could create personalized plans more easily than in a general classroom. Likewise, it is in the distinct classroom where educators can instruct, conduct functional evaluations, and offer the necessary support.

In my opinion, children with intellectual disabilities should receive training in a separate class to facilitate activity-based learning, modeling, and the integration of school-home activities. In the designated class, we can assist children in enhancing their functional skills. Individuals who can manage themselves are now able to join inclusive classrooms, while others may focus on acquiring functional and life skills needed for survival; thus, an adapted curriculum is necessary (Teacher Special 1, 2024).

While teachers trained in special education believed in promoting learning in a separate classroom and offering functional assessments, general education teachers, who lack special education training, thought that including students with disabilities hampers school performance since they struggle academically and can be challenging to teach.

I believe the government should create specialized schools for children with intellectual disabilities. In a typical classroom setting, they present numerous challenges such as failing, distracting during lessons, and at times, they become a burden to their peers who must provide care for these students (Teacher 7, 2024).

4.3 Teaching strategies for children with intellectual impairments

The study investigated teaching strategies to determine how much they contribute to enhancing the academic performance of children with intellectual disabilities. Educational institutions that employ diverse methods to provide teaching to address students' needs have effectively facilitated learning for children with intellectual disabilities. Teachers employing interactive pedagogies excelled, while those utilizing non-interactive methods did not perform well. This poses a significant challenge in teaching, as our instructional resources are created locally, making it challenging to apply methods and approaches with unclear teaching materials.

As an educator, I constantly face challenges with my instructional techniques. However, some of the strategies and techniques I employ include engaging parents and guardians in their children's development, incorporating peers in the classroom, using participatory methods in small groups, picture illustrations, and applying techniques of positive reinforcement (Teacher 3, 2024).

These results suggest that the majority of teachers employed the lecture method, which is a non-interactive approach, contributing to the students' inadequate performance (Knight et al., 2019). As per the modeling by Knight et al. (2019), practices involving environmental structure and those with various specified components (for instance, pivotal response treatment, picture exchange communication system) are most beneficial for children with intellectual disabilities. The result aligns with Vuzo (2010), who observed that learners collaborate through interaction to develop intellectual and practical activities that influence the structure and content of the subject matter. However, this scenario is not frequently observed in primary schools during the teaching and learning process, resulting in passive learning. A teacher of children with intellectual disabilities suggested employing active teaching techniques.

I typically employ teaching techniques that assist me in capturing the attention of my students. I utilize images; I split my students into small teams, I employ the reinforcement method, I incorporate tangible materials that my students can see and touch, and I also adopt the strategy of involving parents (Teacher 5, 2024).

The results align with Jones (1986), indicating that teachers who possess a solid understanding of the uniqueness of learners requiring special education may be more effective in instructing them. He contends that mainstream teachers lacking experience in inclusive education feel anxious about accommodating students with special needs in their classrooms. Consequently, inadequate performance among students with intellectual disabilities can be linked to the teacher's inability to impart essential knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to the students.

Conclusion

There is an insufficient availability of resources to improve inclusive education for children with intellectual disabilities, such as infrastructure, teaching and learning materials, qualified educators, and a negative attitude from parents towards the education of children with intellectual disabilities. Teachers employ less suitable curriculum implementation methods, utilizing unfriendly strategies for applying the general curriculum to children with intellectual impairments, which results in poor performance and increased school drop-out rates; furthermore, due to the absence of an adapted curriculum, some children remain in school longer, hoping they will eventually succeed. The perspectives of teachers, learners, and parents regarding classroom teaching methods for children with intellectual disabilities that enhance academic success are insufficient, as many teachers report using the standard curriculum, while these children may require modified activities. Additionally, parents are seldom involved in aiding their education.

Recommendation for Action

Governments must create a favorable environment in primary schools that boosts enrollment of pupils with special needs, particularly those with intellectual impairments, to effectively implement inclusive education in standard schools and classrooms. The government needs to focus on training teachers in special education for children with intellectual disabilities to enhance availability in primary schools, ensuring equity, quality, and inclusive education. The government, in partnership with various educational stakeholders, is working to acquire appropriate teaching and learning resources and to create tailored curricula for students with special needs in secondary schools, aiming to enhance the teaching and learning experience for those with intellectual disabilities. Primary schools, in partnership with stakeholders, develop plans tailored to their environment to assist and promote a conducive learning atmosphere for pupils with intellectual impairments within an inclusive educational framework. The Tanzanian government recognizes all children with intellectual disabilities in the community and students in primary schools to provide assistance based on their needs.

Recommendation for Further Studies

Additional research may concentrate on the execution of curriculum in inclusive environments for children with intellectual disabilities. Research of various kinds aimed at improving the inclusivity of children with intellectual disabilities across different educational tiers in Tanzania is essential for fostering supportive learning environments for every student in basic and higher education.

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